

ortho-phenylenediamine(Gulland and Virden *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 930).

The present work mainly deals with the properties of the azlactone and its condensation product with *p*-toluidine, α -naphthylamine and aniline. The condensation was effected by the method of Narang and Rây (*ibid.*, 1931, 976).

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of the azlactone from 6-aldehydocoumarin.—A mixture of the aldehyde (10 g.), hippuric acid (10 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.) together with freshly distilled acetic anhydride (17 c.c.) was heated in a flask on a water-bath for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The yellow mass so obtained was washed several times with alcohol and repeatedly boiled with a large volume of water to remove the excess of hippuric acid and filtered. The residual mass was boiled twice with considerable amount of 80 p.c. alcohol to remove the unreacted-upon aldehyde and it was finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid in lusturous yellow needles, m.p. 245° , yield 6 p.c. (Found: C, 71.8; H, 3.49; N, 4.4. $C_{19}H_{11}O_4N$ requires C, 71.92; H, 3.47; N, 4.41 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the Azlactone and Isolation of Coumarin-6-pyruvic Acid in the form of Quinoxalino Compound.

The hydrolysis of the azlactone was effected by heating it with 10 p.c. caustic soda solution until the evolution of ammonia had ceased. The solution was then saturated with sulphur dioxide and filtered. The filtrate was boiled with hydrochloric acid when the keto-acid separated as a tarry mass which resisted all attempts for crystallisation. It however condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine,

when alcoholic solution of the two were shaken together. The quinoxalino-compound separated from acetic acid in light grey rhombic plates, m.p. 288-90°. (Found: C, 70.78; H, 3.95; N, 9.08. $C_{18}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires C, 71.05; H, 3.61; N, 9.21 per cent.).

Condensation of the azlactone with p-toluidine.—Azlactone (9 g.) was heated with p-toluidine (3 g.) and a trace of copper-bronze at 150-60° for 2 hours. The cooled mass was extracted with hot acetic acid from which reddish brown silky crystalline plates of the compound having the formula $C_9H_5O_2CH:C(NH\cdot C_6H_4\cdot CH_3)\cdot CONH\cdot C_6H_4\cdot CH_3$, separated. It was recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 258°. (Found: C, 73.55; H, 5.21; N, 6.66. $C_{26}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 73.58; H, 4.95; N, 6.6 per cent.).

Condensation of the azlactone with α -naphthylamine.—The azlactone (9 g.) was similarly condensed with α -naphthylamine (4 g.) by heating the mixture at a temperature of 150° and the product was extracted with glacial acetic acid (charcoal) as yellowish needles of $C_9H_5O_2CH:C(NH\cdot C_6H_4)\cdot CO\cdot NHC_{10}H_7$. (Found: C, 75.37; H, 4.7; N, 6.07. $C_{29}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires C, 75.65; H, 4.35; N, 6.08 per cent.).

Condensation of the azlactone with aniline.—The azlactone was similarly condensed with aniline by heating equimolecular proportions of the two in the presence of a little copper-bronze at 130-40° for 1½ to 2 hours. The tarry viscous mass was treated with hot glacial acetic acid in which the compound was soluble. The acetic acid solution was boiled several times with charcoal and the clear solution on concentration yielded yellowish white needle shaped crystals of the compound. $C_9H_5O_2CH:C(NH\cdot C_6H_5)\cdot CONHPh$, m.p. 178-80°. (Found: C, 72.98; H, 4.87; N, 6.79. $C_{25}H_{18}O_4N_2$ requires C, 73.17; H, 4.4; N, 6.88 per cent.).

In conclusion I wish to express my sincere thanks to Sir P. C. Rây for his kind interest in this investigation.

